

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

CREATING A NEW CULTURAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE 1920S IN UKRAINE

Dramaretskyi B.

PhD (History)

Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, associate Professor

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3569-6784>

Abstract

The article examines how the worldview in the 1920s was shaped with the help of comprehensive ideology, control over the media of that time and absolute subordination of creative intellectuals who influenced public opinion by the Soviet party-state group with terrorist methods. Having seized power in Ukraine through the spread of false promises, local collaborators and direct aggression, the Bolshevik Party began with a total take of the population and terror and at the same time instilling ideology, trying to replace it with traditional culture. Significant attention was paid to well-known figures in society, using propaganda and artistic means to form and spread the communist worldview in society, and the only criterion for evaluating works of art was the ideological component. The system of total control was embodied. *Intimidation, harassment, arrests, camps and killings began.* In fact, culture, education and science became an appendage to the norms and rules of social behaviour established by the Bolsheviks. *And already in the second half of the 1920s, the task was fulfilled, and heavy industry enterprises were built at an accelerated pace, Ukrainisation was curtailed, and a single ideology prevailed.*

Keywords: Ukraine, society, artists, consciousness, Bolsheviks, cultural policy, terrorist methods.

Creating a New Cultural Environment in the 1920s in Ukraine

Problem statement

Today Ukrainian society is at the turn of the epoch. It is not only about the latest technologies that have become part of our lives but also a radical transformation of worldview. The transition from traditional information systems (printed products, radio and television) to innovative ones means that information has become publicly available, is immediately disseminated, and is much more difficult to control or impose censorship restrictions. However, there are new challenges related to regulating the information field at the state level, manipulating consciousness, and protecting the individual from the spread of fake information.

The successors of the Bolshevik crimes and unprecedented lies, the modern Russian leadership, educated its population on propaganda similar to the Bolshevik and Goebbels (considering modern technology). No wonder 81% of Russians support the actions of the Russian army in Ukraine (a poll conducted by the Levada Centre NGO, which the Russian government considers a "foreign agent") [19]¹. At the same time, Russia is destroying any reports that contradict its propaganda line about the invasion of Ukraine as a "special military operation" [6]².

A similar situation was already in the 1920s when the party-state group managed to change the population's worldview in almost the entire Russian Empire. The Bolsheviks controlled not only the media

but also any other communicative environment from print and radio to everyday communication with colleagues, neighbours, conversations "in the kitchen", jokes, etc. And if publishing houses (printing houses, cinemas, photos, etc.) were enough to take away from the owners, nationalise and personally decide which products to release and which to ban, it was a bit more difficult to influence public opinion. What was needed was a strong ideology and the control of the whole society. Particular attention was paid to those who had public authority, whose words were listened to, and who could influence the mass consciousness. First of all, it concerned social and political figures, representatives of culture, education, and science. And here, the Bolshevik government did not stop at anything. Any "deviations" from Lenin's understanding of the construction of communism, not to mention ideological and political opponents, were perceived as hostile and subject to elimination. Then, it was the turn of representatives of the creative intelligentsia. Initially, they were used as a universal tool to destroy the previous worldview. Traditional ideas, holidays, and even faith replaced Soviet, artificial ones. Historical events were distorted or silenced, famous historical figures were watered down, new holidays, new rites were created, a pantheon of "gods" (Marx-Engels-Lenin, and then Stalin) was formed, and there were "heroes" (Chapaev, Shchors, Pavlik Morozov). etc.). And when this task was accomplished, all figures of culture, education, and science, who did not agree to glorify the Bolshevik ideology, in the version pointed

¹Moiseev V. For most Russians, the war in Ukraine evokes a sense of "pride in Russia" - a poll. // The page. News. 2022, April 4. / <https://thepage.ua/ua/news/opituvannya-levada-centru-shodo-stavlennya-rosiyan-do-vijni-v-ukrayini>

²Hamilton I.A. Russia is playing whack-a-mole as it repeatedly blocks niche parts of the internet spreading information

about Ukraine, including a pet grooming site, a scary story blog, and a sudoku site. // Business Insider, May 8, 2022. / <https://www.businessinsider.com/russia-playing-whack-a-mole-ukraine-anti-war-information-online-2022-5>

out by the leaders, were subject to criticism, censorship, and prohibition. *Dissenters were intimidated, persecuted, imprisoned and killed.* "Soviet experiments with memory were aimed at educating the "new man", teaching him how to speak "correctly", presenting himself, his team, his work, to demonstrate their faith in a bright socialist future" [12; p.2]³.

The rudiments of the cultural environment created in the 1920s can still be observed today. No wonder, until the last days of the USSR, in Ukrainian schools, the Russian language was called the "native language", intensive study of Russian literature, and teachers who taught it received a higher salary. Instead, Ukrainian language and literature were optional subjects and could be waived by writing a statement. Therefore, it is not surprising that now actively used the "Russian-speaking population" concept and associated with it "Russian world". "All of this is an objective legacy of colonial/neocolonial times from the mental, deeply subconscious guidelines that are rooted in the culture of everyday life and were formed during the periods of the division of Ukraine between certain states and ending with various measures of economic and cultural integration of the country's regions to the former "All-Union" (Russian-imperial) space" [7]⁴. Part of the population still nostalgically remembers the Soviet past, talking about stability, victory and "respect" around the world. No wonder, in preparation for the war against Ukraine, Russia's special services worked with the help of collaborators and through propaganda. Their task was to maximise the Russification of Ukraine and the introduction of puppet power in the state [9]⁵. As a result, men were brought up who were hostile to Ukrainian culture, history and language. In no democratic country in the world can it be imagined that a national minority could force a titular nation to speak the language of that national minority, refusing to learn the language and know the culture of the country in which it lives.

Source and Literature Analysis

3Klymenko O.M. Construction of the memory of the "new man" in the 1920s-1930s (on the materials of the USSR): dis. for science. stup. can. histories. Science 07.00.01. - history of Ukraine / O.M. Klymenko O.M.. Kyiv, 2018 P.2.

4Hrabovskiy S., Losiev I. Ukrainian identity: problems and challenges. / Day, 2013. No 207 / <https://day.kyiv.ua/uk/article/tema-dnya-cuspilstvo/ukrayinska-identichnist-problemita-vikliki>

5Dumanska V. The Ghost of Nazism in Ukraine: How the Kremlin Worked with Collaborators for Decades Ukrainian Truth. April 13, 2022. / [HTTPS://WWW.PRAVDA.COM.UA/COLUMNS/2022/04/13/7339061/INDEX.AMP](https://WWW.PRAVDA.COM.UA/COLUMNS/2022/04/13/7339061/INDEX.AMP)

6Kuts O. Ukrainisation as a catalyst for the spiritual life of Ukrainian society in the 20s and 30s. // Scientific notes of the Institute of Political and Ethnonational Studies. IF Kuras NAS of Ukraine. 2006. Vip. 32. pp. 224-232; Maliy K. Ukrainisation of education in the 1920s // *Ridna shkola*. 1996, -12 18; Idris N. Anti-Ukrainian sentiments in the cities of the USSR during the era of Ukrainisation "in the 20s - early 30s of the twentieth century. // *Mandrivets: All-Ukrainian Scientific Journal*, 2010. No 5. pp. 36-39; Parakhina M. Theory of the struggle of two cultures "- in search of Russian-Ukrainian historiographical consensus (past and present of one concept). // Ukrainian historical collection, Vol. 15, 2012. pp. 303-316.

In modern domestic historiography, many scientific papers are devoted to the Bolshevik cultural policy of the 1920s. Ukrainisation was considered in the studies of O. Kuts, K. Maliy, N. Idris, M. Parakhina, studying not only the positive changes in Ukrainian society and the revival of spiritual life, but also anti-Ukrainian sentiments that were widespread in the Russified cities of the USSR [15, pp. 224-232; 18, pp. 12 18; 10, pp. 36-39; 23, pp. 303-316]⁶. Significant attention was paid to publishing (M. Andriichuk⁸) and the formation of censorship bodies, as the entire cultural sphere of Ukraine came under the comprehensive control of the totalitarian system (I. Avtushenko⁹). Works on party-state political terrorism occupy a significant place. Yes, Yu. Lavrynenko emphasises that Stalin's terror was an "ideological" terror, which included all the dissidents from Lenin's allies to the intelligentsia [16, 976 p.]¹⁰. The publication "Political Terror and Terrorism in Ukraine in the 19 - 20 centuries" became extremely important. There is the Institute of History of Ukraine of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, which, based on a comprehensive source base, comprehends the problem of Soviet terror [24, 952 p.]¹¹.

In our opinion, research on the definition of Bolshevik methods of implementing the "cultural revolution" in Ukraine deserves special attention. In particular, S. Kulchytskyi emphasises that the socio-political system established by the Bolsheviks absorbed the revolutionary energy of the masses and enslaved them more profound. More subtly than all the states are known to humanity, defining what the communist leaders called socialism, more precisely Leninist-Stalinist communist socialism [14].¹² M. Frolov studied the concept of Bolshevik policy on the formation of the proletarian state¹³, K. Nikitenko considered the destructive influence of Stalin's repressions against the intelligentsia, which dealt an irreparable blow to Ukrainian culture, destroying the nation's elite [20, pp. 12-26].¹⁴ Klymenko O.M.

⁸ Andriichuk M. Vydavnycha sprava u pidradianskii Ukraini v mizhvoiennyi period [Publishing in sub-Soviet Ukraine in the interwar period] // *Tekhnolohiia i tekhnika drukarstva*. 2015. No 1 (47). p. 103-115.

⁹ Avtushenko I. (2000) Vplyv komunistychnoho totalitarnoho rezhymu na kulturnyi rozvytok Ukrainy [The influence of the communist totalitarian regime on the cultural development of Ukraine] (1920 — persha polovyna 1930-h rr.) // *Etnichna istoriia narodiv Yevropy*. Vyp. 5. p. 118-122.

¹⁰ Lavrynenko Yu. Shot revival: Anthology 1917-1933: Poetry - prose - drama - essay / edited, foreword, afterword by Yu. Lavrynenko; afterword by E. Sverstyuk. Kyiv: Smoloskyp, 2008. 976 p.

¹¹ Political terror and terrorism in Ukraine. 19 - 20 centuries. Historical essays / D.V. Bishop, O.G. Bazhan, T.V. Bykova and others; resp. ed. V.A. Resins. Kyiv: Nauk. Dumka, 2002. 952 p.

¹² Kulchytskyi S. How Leninist-Stalinist Communist Socialism Was Created / Week ua, January 11 2016. / <https://tyzhden.ua/History/229576>

¹⁴ Nikitenko K. Culture and society: the conflict between totalitarian and personal (on the example of the era of Stalinism) // *Bulletin of the LNAM. Series: Cultural Sciences*, 2016. Issue. 29. pp. 12-26.

studied, on the example of writing the history of Dniproges, the memory construction of the "new man" in the USSR [12]¹⁵15.

The purpose of the article is to study the Bolshevik policy and the methods of its implementation for creating a new cultural environment in Ukraine.

Main Research Material

Taking advantage of the political expectations of the population of the vast empire of peace, social justice, freedom and democracy, the Bolshevik leaders with populist slogans: "peace to the people", "factories, plants", "land to the peasants", "all power to the Soviets", etc., managed to influence the emotional state of some citizens, especially its Lumpenproletariat-oriented layer, to arouse hatred for the existing political system and increase their supporters. Moreover, most people did not understand politics, economics, international relations or cultural priorities. "Leaders of the Bolshevik faction of the Russian Social Democrats gained popularity among the people due to populist demagoguery invented a workers' and peasants' state in which workers and peasants did not have the right to vote, and then using propaganda and mass terror created an unnatural, existing only in their heads socio-economic system" [14].¹⁶16

From the point of view of Bolshevik leaders, communist ideology was to become all-encompassing, replace traditional culture, and create new rituals, cults, myths, and gods. By instilling their ideology and creating political myths, the communist elite consciously cultivated the idea of its inseparable unity with the population, of the fact that it is a people's government "which in one fell swoop" is building a communist society.

And if, in the early stages, the Bolsheviks managed to deceive part of the population with populist promises and rely on local collaborators and direct aggression to establish power, then setting control over the occupied territory of Ukraine was a difficult task. In reality, their policies in the economy and culture have led to catastrophe and hatred.

No freedom was involved. Lenin also clarified this: "The language of equality, freedom and democracy in the current situation is nonsense. We are waging a class struggle, and our goal is to destroy the classes. As long as workers and peasants remain, socialism remains unfulfilled" [17, т. 40, pp. 304.]¹⁸18. Bolshevik leaders were also confident in their ability to arbitrarily define the borders of states [25, p. 145]¹⁹19, as they were aimed not at the free, democratic development of nation-states, but at the world

proletariat, the world revolution. Therefore, with the admiration of Ukraine, the majority of party members barely hid their hatred for everything Ukrainian, as well as for the existence of Ukrainian statehood in general, despite the demagoguery about the right of nations to self-determination. This was understandable because the Bolshevik leadership had imperial views (not only of Russians but of Russified Jews, Ukrainians, Georgians, etc., who were even more chauvinistic, constantly "proving" their affiliation with the Vylikoros (Great Russian – *tr.*)).

The bastions of the new government were Ukrainian cities, where about 80% of the members of the Communist Party of Ukraine lived, at the same time; the composition of the population was inversely proportional. And it was in the cities of the USSR that manifestations of Ukraine phobia took the sharpest forms [10, p. 36].²⁰20 Therefore, with the establishment of the Bolshevik regime in Ukraine, the previous imperial cultural and national policy was continued. Despite the proclaimed slogans of free culture development, language and various freedoms, the policy of Russification was maintained, and attempts at national cultural revival were severely halted. It meant that the use of the Ukrainian language, and its introduction into cultural and educational institutions was prohibited.

The Bolshevik Party also opposed all those who owned property, not just the "exploiters" and "oppressors". Unprecedented looting of the urban population began, church property was taken away, and grain was confiscated from peasants. And if the resistance to the communist government in the cities was suppressed by violence, then in the countryside, the government failed. Back in March-April 1919, peasants began protesting in Ukraine against the policy of military communism under the slogans "Down with the Commune!", "For Soviet Power - without Communists!" The anti-Bolshevik insurgents, united in more than 100 detachments, numbered more than 40,000. In the South, with the peasantry's support, Nestor Makhno fought until August 1921. The insurgent movement penetrated the ranks of the Red Army and blocked the work of state economic bodies, industrial enterprises, transport [22, p.15]²¹21. Ukrainians also remembered the Russian interventions well, despite attempts to cover them up with statements about "internal conflict" and "civil war". It became increasingly clear to the population that "with the conquest of Ukraine, the occupiers needed fuel from the Donetsk basin, sources of bread and food" [17, т. 38., p. 313].²²22.

¹⁵¹⁵Klymenko O.M. Constructing the memory of the "new man" in the 1920s-1930s (based on the materials of the USSR): Abstract. for science. stup. can. histories. Science 07.00.01. - history of Ukraine / Klymenko O.M. Kyiv, 2018.

¹⁶¹⁶Kulchytskyi S. How Leninist-Stalinist Communist Socialism Was Created / Week ua, January 11 2016. / <https://tyzhden.ua/History/229576>

¹⁸¹⁸Ленин В.И. Полное собрание починений. Москва, 1970. Т.40. С. 304.

¹⁹¹⁹Frolov M.O. Transformation of the Bolsheviks' views on the concept of the proletarian state (1914-1921) // Scientific works of the historical faculty of Zaporizhia State University. 2007. Volume 1 No 21 p. 145.

²⁰²⁰Idris N. Anti-Ukrainian sentiments in the cities of the USSR during the era of Ukrainisation "in the 20s - early 30s of the twentieth century. // Mandrivets: All-Ukrainian Scientific Journal, 2010. No 5. p. 36.

²¹²¹Orlynskyi A.R. Banditry and the struggle against it // Army and Revolution, 1921. No 2. p. 15.

²²²²Lenin V.I. Complete collection of repairs. Moscow, 1970. T.38, p. 313.

Ukrainians were forced to defend their lives and take up arms, and the authorities continued to use terror. Thus use of force: regular army, militia, armed Commission workers, part of the Joint State Political Directorate, didn't give the necessary result. The situation was so threatening that the Labor and Defense Council, headed by Lenin, pointed out that the elimination of "banditry" was a matter of life and death for Soviet Ukraine [11, т. 6., p. 24].²³²³

Thus, the fear of their own existence forced the Bolshevik leadership to change its policy. First, they lost control of the territory and the ability to export resources with it. Not even the vast army and the hated Cheka, which tried to drown Ukraine in blood with the help of the Red Terror, helped. Secondly, in Russia itself, during the same period, there was an uprising of the garrison and crews of warships of the Baltic Fleet in Kronstadt. And to avert the threat and appease the population, in 1921, a new economic policy (NEP) was proclaimed and in 1923, a policy of indigenisation (Ukrainisation).

It is obvious that Ukrainisation was aimed at reassuring the population of Ukraine, which sought national and cultural revival and was outraged by the outright manifestations of Ukraine phobia. The Bolshevik Party decided to expand the use of the Ukrainian language in public institutions, created a network of educational institutions, and the publishing house was translated into Ukrainian. And to increase support for their regime at the national level, as Ukraine's political leadership was largely non-Ukrainian, local Bolsheviks became involved in the political and state apparatus. However, no alternative views on the "guiding role of the Communist Party" were allowed. All, without exception, had to carry out the orders of the central leadership. On the question of national culture, Lenin clearly stated his position: "there is only one solution to the national question (as far as it can be solved in the world of capitalism, the world of profit, gnawing and exploitation), and this solution is consistent democracy", and the slogan of national culture is bourgeois (and often the Black Hundred-clerical) deception. "Our motto is the international culture of democracy and the world labour movement" [17, т. 24, p. 195].²⁵²⁵ Based on this, it becomes clear that all talk about the national language culture development is only a tactical move made for a certain period. And after fulfilling the set tasks, Ukrainisation had to be completed. According to L. Kaganovich, such an achievement was considered deploying new industrial construction in Ukraine [21, p. 92].²⁶²⁶

²³²³History of the Ukrainian SSR. Kyiv, 1977. Т. 6. p. 24.

²⁵²⁵Lenin V.I. Critical notes on the national question. Complete collection of works. Moscow, 1970. Т. 24, p. 195.

²⁶²⁶Nikolayets Yu. O. Settlement structure of the population of Donbass: (ethnopolitical aspect of dynamics) / Monograph. Kyiv: IPIEND named after IF Kuras NAS of Ukraine, 2012. p. 92.

²⁷²⁷Andriichuk M. Publishing in sub-Soviet Ukraine in the interwar period // Technology of Printing. 2015. No 1 (47). p. 105.

²⁸²⁸Kuts O. Ukrainisation as a catalyst for the spiritual life of Ukrainian society in the 20s and 30s. // Scientific notes of

However, Ukrainisation became a stimulus for the cultural revival of Ukraine. The number of publications increased, and in 1931 Ukrainian-language books by name began to predominate in Russian 6,218 titles of Ukrainian publications against 2014 Russian-language titles [2, p. 105].²⁷²⁷ However, this did not apply to circulations, but only to titles, because the number of Russian-language publications prevailed. Printed materials from the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic also continued to arrive. In education, teaching was translated into Ukrainian, reaching 97.2% in 1929 in labour schools, 66% in vocational schools and 40% in higher education [15, p. 225].²⁸²⁸ In culture, new unions of writers and literary associations were organised, new theatres were built (the most famous was "Berezil"), film factories were established in Kyiv, Odesa, and Yalta. Societies and associations of artists of "Red Ukraine" and "Revolutionary Art" were founded.

At the same time, the propaganda component is growing. "Our task is to bring the fighting force of art to the highest social tension, making art the most powerful means of political and world work, i.e. state propaganda of communism... General education is school and extracurricular (including art: theatres, concerts, cinemas, exhibitions, paintings, etc.) ... should be closely linked to communist propaganda" [1, p. 118].²⁹²⁹ Therefore, all cultural figures, as well as educators, were obliged to "glorify" the activities of the Bolsheviks and spread their ideas. The works of art had to correspond to the ideology created by the Bolsheviks, and their artistic value was measured by political and ideological guidelines, which were constantly changing during the 1920s. "Artists glorified the "man of labour", and cartoonists created images of enemies. Everyone built a fictional world to the best of their ability and talent. *According to the laws of parallel lines, newspaper columns, literary works, and even school textbooks, all lived their own lives with almost no contact with reality. The main law of Soviet art was formulated unambiguously. Creative personalities were transformed into loyal slaves of the regime*" [20, p. 17].³⁰³⁰

Both the party leadership and the Russified population of Ukraine were highly negative about Ukrainisation. In practice, this meant that the study of the Ukrainian language was introduced formally. Soviet lower-level officials simply "spent time" training for a possible promotion, following instructions they did not understand, and middle-ranking civil servants could barely conceal their reluctance to Ukrainianise. Typical of that time is the

the Institute of Political and Ethnonational Studies. IF Kuras NAS of Ukraine. 2006. Vol. 32. p.225.

²⁹²⁹Autushenko I. The influence of the communist totalitarian regime on the Ukraine cultural development (1920 - first half of the 1930's) // Ethnic History of the Peoples of Europe, 2000. Issue. 5. p.118

³⁰³⁰Nikitenko K. Culture and society: the conflict between totalitarian and personal (on the example of the era of Stalinism) // Bulletin of the LNAM. Series: Cultural Sciences. Vol. 29, 2016. p.17.

statement of one of the heads of the department of public education: "I don't know the language, I don't want to learn it, but I can sing a Ukrainian song" [18, p. 29]³¹. Finally, a negative attitude towards national policy was manifested among the top leaders of Ukraine. It was the second secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party (b) D. Lebed, who, on 17 March 1923, published in *The Communist* newspaper an article "Some Issues of the Party Congress", in which he justified the struggle of two cultures. According to his theory, Russian culture is progressive, urban, will inevitably defeat the Ukrainian - backward, rural [23, p. 307]³². So why should a "true communist" study backwards culture if even the "leader of the world proletariat" Lenin considered national culture a manifestation of liberal-bourgeois nationalism, corrupting the working class and causing significant damage to freedom and class struggle? The national culture of the bourgeoisie is a fact (and, I repeat, the bourgeoisie everywhere conducts agreements with landlords and priests). Militant bourgeois nationalism dulls, deceives, and divides workers to lead them to the bourgeoisie and this is the basic fact of our time" [17, т. 24, p. 195]³³.

Ukrainephobia was most active in Russified cities and the south-eastern part of the USSR. It is since, firstly, the Ukrainian leadership, at all levels, was mostly Russian or Russified, and secondly, the policy of industrialisation led to the Lumpenproletariat-oriented population, which was Russified, did not know and did not want to learn Ukrainian, nor culture, thirdly, the implementation of active migration policy from the Russian regions, especially during the famine of 1921-1923 and industrialisation.

The construction of new enterprises took place mainly in eastern Ukraine, port cities, primarily Odesa, and the largest commercial and industrial centres - Kharkiv and Kyiv, and it is in these regions is the growth of Russians, where it is in these regions about 3/4 of Russians live [5]³⁴. Russians did not want to integrate into Ukrainian culture, demanded that Ukrainians speak Russian, etc., against which there were numerous conflicts [21, p. 90-92]³⁵. The growth of the Russian population in Ukrainian industrial areas also remained an important factor in the subordination of Ukrainian industrial areas to the Moscow centre.

It should be noted that the manifestations of great-power chauvinism took place at all levels. On the social level, it is a contemptuous, intolerant attitude towards

everything Ukrainian, especially the language, and even a denial of the right of Ukrainians to exist as a separate ethnic group. Psychologically and stereotypically, it is the use of offensive ethnonyms (Little Russians, Ukrainians), attributing certain negative traits to the whole nation. Ideologically and politically, it is the "substantiation" of the famous thesis about the victory of the highest Russian culture of the proletariat and the demise of Ukrainian peasant culture; this is a purposeful incitement to hatred of Ukrainians as a means of achieving political goals, aggressive and imperial ambitions, etc [10, p. 37]³⁶.

It is obvious that cultural figures could not stand aside from outright anti-Ukrainian manifestations. For example, in 1928, M. Kulish published the *Mina Mazailo* play, in which the protagonist "not that ... does not want to listen to Ukrainians, but on the contrary - wants to change our Russian surname and already asks his teacher to be able to teach him to speak Russian correctly, for example, not "sapohy (boots - tr.)", but "spagi" [13]³⁷. At the same time, representatives of the Ukrainian creative intelligentsia, as public opinion leaders, have always been under close scrutiny. It was not enough for Bolshevik ideologues to spread their own speeches that would prove the progressiveness of socialist construction and raise the importance of its new representative, the proletariat [8, p. 54]³⁸. Soviet and party functionaries needed to attract the maximum number of well-known figures in society, using propaganda and artistic, and scientific means to shape public opinion by spreading the Soviet vision. "There are no forms of science and art that are not associated with the great ideas of communism and ... work on building a communist economy", - said in 1919 at the 8th Congress of the Russian Communist Party. In fact, art, education and science became an appendage to the norms and rules of social behaviour established by the Bolsheviks. *Communist leaders pointed out how to work, how to behave in everyday life, what a family should be, who to hate, whom to love, etc., and cultural figures had to create relevant works of art, scholars - to justify the inevitable "victory of communism", educators - to shape children have a communist worldview. Everything was aimed at creating a "new man" who, according to the cultural ideas of the Bolsheviks, was deprived of individual traits, and all the life of the individual was to be subordinated to a single goal. In fact, the most striking*

31 ³¹Малій К. Українізація освіти у 20-ті роки // Рідна школа. 1996, № 11-12. С.29.

32 ³²Парахіна М. Теорія боротьби двох культур» — у пошуках російсько-українського історіографічного консенсусу (минуле і сучасне однієї концепції). // Український історичний збірник, 2012. Вип. 15. С.307.

33 ³³Ленин В.И. Критические заметки по национальному вопросу. Полное собрание сочинений. Москва, 1970. Т. 24. С. 195.

34 ³⁴Всесоюзная перепись населения 1926 г.: УССР. Итоги по республике. Полесский подрайон. Отдел переписи: Народность. Родной язык. Грамотность. Т. 11 / Труды ЦСУ СССР. М.: Изд. ЦСУ СССР, 1929.

35 ³⁵Ніколаєць Ю. О. Поселенська структура населення Донбасу: (етнополітичний аспект динаміки) / Монографія. Київ: ІПіЕНД ім. І.Ф. Кураса НАН України, 2012. С. 90-92

36 ³⁶Ідріс Н. Антиукраїнські настрої у містах УСРР за доби українізації» у 20 — на початку 30-х рр. ХХ ст. // Мандрівець: Всеукраїнський науковий журнал, 2010. № 5. С. 37.

37 ³⁷Куліш М.Г. Мина Мазайло. Перша дія. 1. // Бібліотека української літератури. / <https://www.ukrlib.com.ua/books/printit.php?tid=1087>

38 ³⁸Dramaretsky B. On the question of studying the manifestations of "social deviations" in the cities of Soviet Ukraine in the 1920-1930s // Scientific Historical and Philosophical Journal of the University", -1-6, 2014. p.54.

analogy is man, as a part, the cog of the general mechanism — the masses.

It should be noted that there was no total control in the first half of the 1920s. Many artists were fascinated by revolutionary romance and believed in the proclaimed slogans of freedom, peace, justice, universal equality, etc. They also believed in the policy of Ukrainisation as an opportunity to develop Ukrainian culture, a language that had long been banned and suppressed in the Russian Empire. They enthusiastically began to develop national culture, and experimented with various art forms and means, creating works of art. However, they came across the harsh reality of human lawlessness, political terror, hunger, and the permissiveness of party officials. And, like empathetic people, they could not remain silent. Mykola Kulish wrote "Play 97", "Mina Mazailo", Ivan Bahrianyi "Tiger Hunters", "Garden of Gethsemane", Vasily Barka "Yellow Prince", Alexander Dovzhenko "Diary", and others and all these works will be banned, and their authors will be arrested, imprisoned, encamped or killed. Gradually, the party leadership began to implement a system of total control over cultural life.

Note that during the struggle for power between J. Stalin and L. Trotsky, and later with L. Kamenevym and H. Zinovievym, the main task of the Party was to destroy the previous cultural environment; until then, new artistic trends (futurism, neo-classics, etc.) were perceived as appropriate. Such works, if not popularised, in contrast to the consonant ideas of communism, then, in any case, were not banned. But then the situation changed. Like any other opponents of the Bolshevik Party, political opponents were destroyed, and the country moved to peacebuilding. All artistic searches, new genres, etc. became unnecessary. Artists are subject to criticism, censorship, and various bans. Ukrainisation is also curtailed. Soviet leaders who supported Ukrainisation and were too "independent" are accused of national evasion and cultural figures of bourgeois nationalism. For example, in 1927, the People's Commissar for Education O. Shumsky was forced to repent, transferred to Moscow, and then arrested. Only 8.2% of the Communists who joined the party before 1920 remained in the 1930s. [4, p. 85; 24, p. 441]⁴⁰⁴⁰

Dissenters were harshly stigmatised in the media (newspapers, radio) and held appropriate meetings in schools and enterprises, not allowing their arguments to be heard. It was accompanied by mass hysteria demanding the punishment of enemies of the people, and society formed the idea of self-sacrifice in the name of communist ideals and hatred of enemies named by

the authorities and those who held a different position were physically destroyed.

Most cultural figures were repressed and physically exterminated. Even loyal to the government representatives of the creative intelligentsia, who tried to talk about some kind of autonomy, focus on the best world standards, adherence to high standards, attempts to declare that culture is out of politics, were subject to criticism, silence, censorship, repression. For example, Ivan Bagryany, who went through all the tortures of Stalin's camps, later wrote in exile: "I do not want to return to the USSR, because the Stalinist socialist USSR is a continuous concentration camp of enslaved people of all 100 nationalities - people without rights, stereotyped, hungry and poor. For a quarter of a century, they received nothing from Bolshevism except prisons, rivers of blood and tears... And they will get nothing as long as Bolshevism" exists [3]⁴²⁴². Back in 1954, the congress of the Association of Ukrainian Writers "Word" in New York determined that only by 1938 the communist regime "removed from literature" and actually killed 223 Ukrainian writers, of whom 192 were shot or killed in camps, eight could not stand psychological and physical abuse and committed suicide, seven died their deaths and sixteen went missing. However, the Congress stressed that these data are very approximate [16, p. 13]⁴³⁴³. In general, according to scientists from the Institute of History of Ukraine, during the 1920s - 1950s, the USSR repressed 2,000 writers, about 1,500 died in prisons and camps before they had the freedom [P24, p.438]⁴⁴⁴⁴.

It should be noted that captured by the Russians, Ukraine was repressed throughout the Soviet era. Thus, in 1985 the outstanding Ukrainian poet Vasyl Stus was killed, whom Nobel Laureate A. Sakharov and leader of the Ukrainian national-democratic liberation movement of the 80-90s, Hero of Ukraine — V. Chornovil called "conscience of the era and pure soul". And in 1989, the last soldier of the Ukrainian Insurgent Army, Ivan Honcharuk, was convicted and killed.

Conclusions

Thus, thanks to military aggression, populist promises to fulfil the people's hopes and relying on local collaborators, the Bolshevik Party established power in Ukraine. The policy pursued by the Russian Communist Party was to plunder the entire country and establish strict control through "red terror". The Communists did not hide their goal, in particular, "rob the loot" and could barely contain their hatred for everything Ukrainian. And to better implement their plan, considerable attention was paid to the planting of ideology, trying to replace it with traditional culture.

⁴⁰⁴⁰Borysenko M. (2010) Zmina zmistu dozvillia zhyteliv mist Ukrainy [Changing the content of leisure in the cities of Ukraine] v 20-30-ky rokakh XX st. // Naukovyi chasopys NPU imeni M.P. Drahomanova. Istorychni nauky: Zb. naukovykh prats. Vypusk 6: Yuvileinyi vypusk do 175-richchia Natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu imeni M.P. Drahomanova. Kyiv., p. 85.; Political terror and terrorism in Ukraine. The 19th – 20th centuries. Historical essays / D.V. Bishop, O.G. Bazhan, T.B. Bykova and others; resp. ed. V.A. Resins. Kyiv: Scientific Thought, 2002. p. 441.

⁴²⁴²Bahrianyi I. Why don't I want to return to the USSR? / <https://osvita.ua/school/literature/b/66760/list-3.html>

⁴³⁴³Lavrinenko Yu. Shot Revival: Anthology 1917-1933: Poetry - prose - drama - essay / edited, foreword, afterword Lavrinenko Yu. ; afterword by E. Sverstyuk, Kyiv: Smoloskyp, 2002. p.13.

⁴⁴⁴⁴Political terror and terrorism in Ukraine. The 19th -20th centuries. Historical Essays / D.V. Arkhiereyskiy, O.H. Bazhan, T.V. Bykova and others; resp. ed. V.A. Resins. Kyiv: Nauk. Dumka, 2002. p.438

However, popular uprisings and military uprisings caused the Bolsheviks to fear losing control of the occupied territory and their power in general. They changed tactics and, to reassure the people, adopted the NEP and the policy of Ukrainisation, as Ukrainians sought national and cultural revival and were outraged by outright manifestations of Ukraine phobia. But one should not think that the changes took place in the people's interests. Not at all! It was only a temporary retreat for the opportunity to deploy new industrial construction. They wanted a world revolution, and they needed powerful industrial enterprises to produce weapons and related components.

At the same time, Ukrainisation became a stimulus for the cultural revival of Ukraine. The artists were fascinated by revolutionary romance and believed in the proclaimed slogans. *They also believed in the policy of Ukrainisation and the possibility of building Ukrainian culture. However, the Russian party and state leadership and the Russified population of Ukraine negatively perceived Ukrainisation.* Following the instructions of their superiors, they formally implemented the study of the Ukrainian language, and in Russified cities and the south-eastern part of the USSR, Ukraine phobia was generally active. And as long as the party needed to destroy the old culture, it was loyal to the artists and, in the first half of the 1920s, there was no total control. *At the same time, as our own plan is implemented, control and propaganda intensify. The Soviet government needed to attract the maximum number of well-known figures in society, using propaganda and artistic, scientific means to form and spread in society a communist visionary. Gradually, the party leadership began to implement a system of total control. All artistic pursuits became unnecessary, as did talent. The only criterion was the ideological component. The society formed the idea of self-sacrifice in the name of communist ideals and hatred of enemies identified by the authorities.* In fact, culture, education and science became an appendage to the norms and rules of social behaviour established by the Bolsheviks. *Artists are criticised, censored, and banned. Dissenters were stigmatised in the media, and various gatherings, not allowing hearing the accused's arguments.* Intimidation, harassment, arrests, camps and killings began. It was accompanied by mass hysteria demanding the punishment of the people's enemies. Thus, already in the second half of the 1920s, the task set by the Party was fulfilled, heavy industry enterprises were built at an accelerated pace, Ukrainisation was curtailed, and a single ideology prevailed. However, this required the country to be "washed in the blood", turn the population into beggars, and form a cult of personality.

References

1. Avtushenko I. (2000) Vplyv komunistychnoho totalitarnoho rezhymu na kulturnyi rozvytok Ukrainy [The Influence of the Communist Totalitarian Regime on the Cultural Development of Ukraine] (1920 — persha polovyna 1930-h rr.) // *Etnichna istoriia narodiv Yevropy*. Vyp. 5. P. 118-122. [in Ukrainian].

2. Andriichuk M. (2015) Vydavnycha sprava u pidradianskii Ukraini v mizhvoiennyi period [Publishing in sub-Soviet Ukraine in the Interwar Period] // *Tekhnolohiia i tekhnika drukarstva*. No 1(47). p.103-115. / <https://osvita.ua/school/literature/b/66760/list-3.html> [in Ukrainian].

3. Bahrianyi I. (1946) Chomu ya ne khochu veratats do SRSR? [Why I do not want to return to the USSR] / <https://osvita.ua/school/literature/b/66760/list-3.html> [in Ukrainian].

4. Borysenko M. (2010) Zmina zmistu dozvillia zhyteliv mist Ukrainy v 20-30-kh rokakh XX st. [Changing the content of leisure in the cities of Ukraine in the 1920s-1930s] // *Naukovyi chasopys NPU imeni M.P. Drahomanova. Istorychni nauky: Zb. naukovykh prats*. Vypusk 6: Yuvileinyi vypusk do 175-richchia Natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu imeni M.P. Drahomanova. Kyiv,. P. 84-86. [in Ukrainian].

5. Vsesoiuznaia perepys naselenyia 1926 h. (1929) [All-Union Population Census]: USSR. Itohy po respublyke. Poleskyi podraion. Otdel perepysy: Narodnost. Rodnoi yazyk. Hramotnost. T. 11 / Trudi TsSU SSSR. Moskva: Izd. TsSU SSSR. 205 p. [in Russian].

6. Hamilton I.A. (2022) Russia is playing whack-a-mole as it repeatedly blocks niche parts of the internet spreading information about Ukraine, including a pet grooming site, a scary story blog, and a sudoku site. // *Business Insider*, May 8,. / <https://www.businessinsider.com/russia-playing-whack-a-mole-ukraine-anti-war-information-online-2022-5>. [in English].

7. Hrabovskyi S., Losiev I. (2013) Ukrainska identychnist [Ukrainian Identity]: problemy ta vyklyky. / *Den'*, No 207/ <https://day.kyiv.ua/uk/article/temadnya-cuspilstvo/ukrayinska-identychnist-problemi-ta-vykliki> [in Ukrainian].

8. Dramaretskyi B. (2014) Do pytannia vyvchennia proiaviv „sotsialnykh vidkhylen” v mistakh Radianskoi Ukrainy v 1920-1930 rr. [On the question of studying the manifestations of "social deviations" in the cities of Soviet Ukraine in the 1920s -1930s] // *Naukovyi istoryko-filosofskyi zhurnal Universytetu*. No 1-6. pp.53-56. [in Ukrainian].

9. Dumanska V. (2022) Pryvyd natsyzmu v Ukraini [The Ghost of Nazism in Ukraine]: yak kremlivska vlada desiatylittiamy pratsiuvala z kolaborantamy. *Ukrainska pravda*. 13 Kvitnia / <https://www.pravda.com.ua/columns/2022/04/13/7339061/index.amp> [in Ukrainian].

10. Idris N. (2010) Antyukrainski nastroi u mistakh USRR za doby «ukrainizatsii» u 20 – na pochatku 30-kh rr. XX st. [Anti-Ukrainian sentiment in the cities of the USSR during the era of «Ukrainisation" in the 1920s – early 30s] // *Mandrivets: Vseukrainskyi naukovyi zhurnal*. No 5. pp. 36-39 [in Ukrainian].

11. *Istoriia Ukrainskoi RSR (1977)* [History of the Ukrainian SSR]. Kyiv. T. 6. 544 p. [in Ukrainian].

12. Klymenko O. M. (2018) Konstruiuvannia pam'iaty «novoi liudyny» [Building a New Person's Memory] u 1920-kh — 1930 rr. (na materialakh USRR): Dys. na zdobuttia nauk. stup. kan. istor. nauk

07.00.01. – istoriia Ukrainy / O.M. Klymenko. Kyiv. 250 p. [in Ukrainian].

13. Kulish M. H. (1928) Myna Mazailo. [Mina Mazailo]. Persha diia. 1. // Biblioteka ukrainskoi literatury./

<https://www.ukrlib.com.ua/books/printit.php?tid=1087> [in Ukrainian].

14. Kulchytskyi S. (2016) Yak stvoriuvavsia lieninsko-stalinskyi komunososializm [How Leninist-Stalinist Communism-Socialism] / Tyzhden ua, 11 sichnia / <https://tyzhden.ua/History/155673> [in Ukrainian].

15. Kuts O. (2006) Ukrainizatsiia yak katalizator dukhovnoho zhyttia ukrainskoho suspilstva 20-30-kh rokiv [Ukrainisation as a catalyst for the spiritual life of Ukrainian society in the 20s and 30s] // Naukovi zapysky Instytutu politychnykh i etnonatsionalnykh doslidzhen im. I. F. Kurasa NAN Ukrainy. Vyp. 32. pp.224-232. [in Ukrainian].

16. Lavrynenko Yu. (2008) Rozstriliane vidrodzhennia [Shot revival]: Antolohiia 1917-1933: Poeziia — proza — drama — esei / uporiadkuv., peredm., pisliamova Yu. Lavrinenka ; pisliamova Ye. Sverstiuka. Kyiv: Smoloskyp. 976 p. [in Ukrainian].

17. Lenyn V. (1970) O kooperatsyy [About cooperation]. Polnoe sobr. soch., Yzd-vo 5-e. Moskva. T 24; P. 195; T.38, P. 313; T.40. P. 304 [in Russian].

18. Malii K. (1996) Ukrainizatsiia osvity [Ukrainianization of education] u 20-ti roky // Ridna shkola., № 11-12. [in Ukrainian].

19. Moisieiev V. (2022) U bilshosti rosiian viina v Ukraini vyklykaie pochuttia «hordosti za Rosiiu» [For most Russians, the war in Ukraine makes them "proud of Russia"] – opytuvannia. The page. Novyny., 4 kvitnia. / <https://thepage.ua/ua/news/opituvannya-levada-centru-shodo-stavleniya-rosiyan-do-vijni-v-ukrayini>. [in Ukrainian].

20. Nikitenko K. (2016) Kultura i suspilstva: konflikt mizh totalitarnym i osobystym (na prykladi doby stalinizmu) [Culture and society: the conflict between totalitarian and personal (on the example of the Stalinist era)] // Visnyk LNAM. Seria: Kulturolohiya. Vyp. 29. P. 12-26. [in Ukrainian].

21. Nikolaiets Yu. O. (2012) Poselenska struktura naseleння Donbasu: (etnopolitychnyi aspekt dynamiky) [Settlement structure of the population of Donbass: (ethnopolitical aspect of dynamics)] / Monohrafiya. Kyiv: IPIEND im. I. F. Kurasa NAN Ukrainy. 188 p. [in Ukrainian].

22. Orlynskyi A.R. (1921) Bandytyzm y borba s nym [Banditry and the Fight against It] // Armyia y revoliutsiia. №2. [in Russian].

23. Parakhina M. (2012) Teoriia borotby dvokh kultur» — u poshukakh rosiisko-ukrainskoho istoriografichnoho konsensusu (mynule i suchasne odniiei kontseptsii) [The theory of "struggle of two cultures" — in search of Russian-Ukrainian historiographical consensus (past and present of one concept)] // Ukrainskyi istorychnyi zbirnyk, Vyp. 15. P.303-316. [in Ukrainian].

24. Politychnyi teror i teroryzm v Ukraini. XIX-XX st. Istorychni narysy (2002) [Political terror and terrorism in Ukraine. The 19th-20th centuries. Historical Essays] / D. V. Arkhiereiskyyi, O. H. Bazhan, T. V. Bykova ta in.; vidpov. red. V. A. Smolii. Kyiv: Nauk. Dumka. 952 p. [in Ukrainian].

25. Frolov M. O. Transformatsiia pohliadiv bilshovykiv na kontseptsiiu proletarskoi derzhavy (1914-1921 rr.) [Transformation of the Bolsheviks' views on the concept of the proletarian state] // Naukovi pratsi istorychnoho fakultetu Zaporizkoho derzhavnoho universytetu. 2007. Tom 1 № 21 P 144-156. [in Ukrainian].